

Effect of solvents and temperature on the critical micellar concentration of sodium dodecyl sulfate and cetylpyridinium chloride

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The critical micellar concentrations (cmc) of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) in acetonitrile-water media of various compositions have been determined at different temperatures. The cmc of SDS slightly decreases with the increase in acetonitrile concentration and with the increase in temperature, whereas that of CPC increases with the increase in concentration of acetonitrile and temperature. An attempt has been made to explain this type of behaviour. Contrary to the general expectation, the micellization of SDS and CPC in mixed solvents seems to be enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled.

Some studies on the effect of organic additives on the critical micelle concentration (cmc) have been reported, but not much information is available on the effect of mixed solvents on the cmc of surfactants¹⁻⁶. Nevertheless, knowledge of the effect of solvent(s) particularly of mixed solvents, and temperature on cmc of surfactants is essential in the application of surfactants. Here we report the effect of variation of concentration of acetonitrile in acetonitrile-water system on cmc of sodium dodecyl sulfate, SDS (anionic surfactant) and cetyl pyridinium chloride, CPC (cationic surfactant) at various temperatures.

Results and Discussion

The results of the variation in specific conductivities of sodium dodecyl sulfate and cetyl pyridinium chloride with the variation in concentration of surfactants and of acetonitrile in mixed solvents of acetonitrile-water medium are summarized in Tables 1-4. The initial increase in conductivities of surfactants is due to the surfactant ions,

Table 1. Variation in electrical conductivity of sodium dodecyl sulfate in water-acetonitrile mixture at 25°

[SDS] ×10 ⁴ M	Mole fraction of acetonitrile/ (Dielectric constant of the medium ε)					
	0.00 (78.54)	0.01 (78.10)	0.056 (76.08)	0.293 (65.67)	0.404 (60.79)	0.576 (53.23)
	Conductivity (K), m Ω ⁻¹					
9	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.13	0.17
30	0.19	0.20	0.22	0.38	0.45	0.51
50	0.33	0.37	0.40	0.58	0.77	0.82
100	0.60	0.62	0.70	0.91	1.20	1.26
200	0.94	0.90	1.20	1.49	1.82	1.94
300	1.30	1.25	1.72	1.92	2.44	2.67
400	1.48	1.72	2.21	2.40	3.08	3.41
500	1.75	1.89	2.96	2.96	3.66	4.08

Table 2. Effect of variation of concentration of acetonitrile/dielectric constant of acetonitrile-water medium on the cmc of sodium dodecyl sulfate

Mole fraction of acetonitrile	Dielect. const. of medium ε	cmc of SDS × 10 ³ M	-ΔG _M ⁰ kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔH _M ⁰ kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS _M ⁰ kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
0.00	78.54	8.2	32.14		
0.01	78.10	8.1	32.16	4.16	0.094
0.05	76.02	7.8	32.32	3.33	0.097
0.29	65.67	7.0	32.70	3.33	0.099
0.40	60.79	6.6	32.91	2.49	0.102
0.56	53.23	6.4	33.04	4.16	0.097
0.60	52.18	6.0	33.26	1.66	0.106

Table 3. Variation in electrical conductivity of cetylpyridinium chloride in water-acetonitrile mixture at 25°

[SDS] ×10 ⁴ M	Mole fraction of acetonitrile/ (Dielectric constant of the medium ε)						
	0.00 (78.54)	0.103 (74.02)	0.322 (64.39)	0.508 (56.20)	0.716 (47.06)	0.918 (38.21)	1.00 (34.60)
	Conductivity (K), m Ω ⁻¹						
0.08	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01
2.9	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.04
4.5	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.05	0.06
7.4	0.07	0.04	0.08	0.09	0.11	0.11	0.09
9.2	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.10	0.14	0.15	0.10
12.3	0.11	0.11	0.14	0.14	0.17	0.20	0.11
20.3	0.16	0.21	0.20	0.35	0.28	0.37	0.32
33.0	0.21	0.30	0.32	0.47	0.36	0.52	0.44
46.8	0.24	0.53	0.62	0.74	0.74	0.71	0.79
65.6	0.36	0.61	0.78	0.92	0.83	0.99	1.12

whereas at higher concentration, it is mainly due to micelles. The conductivities of surfactants increase with the increase

Table 4. Effect of variation of concentration of acetonitrile/dielectric constant on the cmc of cetylpyridinium chloride at 25°

Mole fraction of acetonitrile	Dielec. const. medium	cmc of CPC $\times 10^4 M$	$-\Delta G_M^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta H_M^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta S_M^\circ$ $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
0.00	78.54	7.0	53.09	41.40	0.0392
0.103	74.02	7.5	52.77	39.08	0.0459
0.322	64.39	8.0	49.72	38.24	0.0385
0.508	56.20	8.9	49.15	38.24	0.0366
0.716	47.06	11.0	45.61	36.58	0.0303
0.918	38.21	21.0	40.63	33.26	0.0247

in concentration of acetonitrile, in acetonitrile-water medium. In general, with the increase in concentration of acetonitrile, the change in slope of the plot of specific conductivity vs concentration of surfactants in mixed solvent of acetonitrile-water (Fig. 1) becomes more and more gradual and some-

Fig. 1. Plot of specific conductivity vs concentration of SDS at 25°.

times it is very difficult to assess the cmc. The cmc of SDS, thus obtained from conductometry, is $8.2 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3} M$ (lit.^{7,8} $7.8-9.1 \times 10^{-3} M$) whereas for CPC it is $7.0 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ (lit.^{7,8} $7.5-9.5 \times 10^{-4} M$). The cmc of SDS slightly decreases (from 8.2×10^{-3} to $6 \times 10^{-3} M$) when the dielectric constant of the medium decreases from 78.54 to 53.61 (Table 2), whereas that of CPC considerably increases (from 7.0×10^{-4} to $21 \times 10^{-4} M$) (Table 4). It may be noted that a break in the plot of σ vs concentration of surfactant does not necessarily mean that cmc has been reached. The present observations goes parallel with that of Corrin and Harkins⁹ and Miyagishi¹⁰ who noticed similar trend in the case of ionic surfactant-dodecylammonium halides, whereas Koshy and Rakshit¹¹ noticed similar trend in the case of Brij-35. However, Singh *et al.*¹ did not find any systematic variation

in cmc values when the surfactants were studied in different solvents. Here it may be mentioned that it has been increasingly clear that molecular interaction in aqueous solvent can not be accounted satisfactorily by considering only the continuous properties of the solvents, such as dielectric constant, instead quite often, the structure of the solvent (whether in pure or mixed system) seems to play an important role. The ionic surfactant in aqueous medium experiences two opposing forces — the hydrophobic interaction which stabilizes the system, and the repulsive force between the ionic head groups which reduces the micellization, and the resultant of these forces can favour/disfavour micellization. So, in the case of SDS, it appears that lowering of cmc is partly due to the reduction of electrostatic repulsion of the head groups of SDS (through solvation of negative end of SDS) and partly due to dispersion forces between the alkyl chains which may dominate, thus leading to the formation of charged micelles at lower concentration. Shinoda¹² on the other hand, tried to explain the decrease in cmc of surfactant in terms of solubilization of an additive in a micelle¹³ whereas Miyagishi¹⁰ explained that the presence of any organic additive may affect the counter ion binding and this may lead to the decrease in cmc of the surfactant. However, in the case of CPC, it is noticed that with the increase in concentration of acetonitrile in water-acetonitrile mixed solvents (i.e. with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium) the cmc increases from 7×10^{-4} to $21.0 \times 10^{-4} M$; similar observations which have been attributed to the solvent power of the mixture, are reported in the literature^{1,4,10,14}. However, Suhick⁶ explained that the increase in cmc may be due to the weaker hydration of halide ions which is difficult to comprehend.

A general equation which relates the variation of cmc of surfactant to the variation of dielectric constant of the medium, temperature and electrolyte concentration etc., is given as²

$$\log C_{\text{cmc}} = Z(1 - \alpha) [\log 2000 \pi \sigma^2 / \epsilon_r RT - \log C_i] + [\Delta G(-\text{CH}_2-)/2.303RT]N + \text{Constant} \quad (1)$$

where Z is the charge on the surfactant ion, σ the surface charge density on the micelle, ϵ_r the dielectric constant of the medium, C_i the concentration of counterion bounded by the micelle, α the fraction of counterions bound by the micelle, T the temperature of the medium and N the total number of carbon atoms in the hydrophobic groups of surfactants. According to the equation, a decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium should increase cmc of the surfactant and that is what has been observed. We feel that the lowering of the dielectric constant can break up the micelle

through an increment in the electrostatic repulsion of the head groups of the micelle surface and a reduction of interfacial energy between the hydrocarbon chain and water (thus reducing the free energy differences between the alkyl chain in the solvent and micellar environment) and thereby altering the cmc³, i.e. the increased structuring in water-acetonitrile liquid system disturbs the formation of micelles by reducing the effectiveness of hydrophobic effect of the surfactant. However, we are not in a position to extend the argument in the case of SDS in which the cmc slightly decreased with the increase in concentration of acetonitrile.

Effect of temperature on cmc : The results of variation of temperature on cmc of SDS and CPC are summarized in Tables 5 and 6. The data reveal that with the increase in temperature (from 25° to 35°), the cmc of SDS slightly decreases and the decrease seems to be real (i.e. above the error limits). Here it may be noted that as the change in cmc is not much one should look at the relative change/trend in cmc values rather than the absolute values. Emerson and Holtzer⁷, and others² also observed similar trend (up to 25°). Moreover, 'the nature of change' depends on the media¹. It may be noted that the effect of temperature on cmc of ionic surfactants is very complex. In micellization, since the transfer of hydrocarbon groups from an aqueous to a non-polar environment (i.e. interior of the micelle) is normally endo-

thermic, one would expect hydrophobic bonds, and thus micelles to become more stable as the temperature is increased, cmc should decrease with the increase in temperature and based on eqn. (1) one can reach the same conclusion. However, as these are ionic surfactants, macroscopic dielectric properties of the medium do have a role to play in stabilizing the micelles. When the temperature of the medium is increased, the decreased dielectric constant of the medium tends to break the micelles, i.e. tends to increase the cmc of the micelles due to the increased repulsive force between the ionic head groups. So, the net effect of these two opposing effects (hydrophobic effect and dielectric effect) can explain the observed effect of temperature on cmc values. The increase in cmc of CPC from 7.0×10^{-4} to 9.0×10^{-4} M in water and 21×10^{-4} to 52×10^{-4} M in acetonitrile-water system ($\epsilon_r = 38.22$) with the increase in temperature from 25 to 35° shows that in the case of CPC, the dielectric effect is more dominant compared to hydrophobic effect. Similar observations are reported for ionic surfactants^{3,7,14}.

Thermodynamic quantities : The formation of micelles in aqueous solution has been attributed to the association of the hydrophobic parts of the surfactants and the repulsion of water of solvation from their immediate environment. The standard free energy of micellization at constant temperature and pressure calculated by using equation¹⁵,

$$\Delta G_M^\circ = (1 + \beta) RT \ln X_{\text{cmc}} \quad (2)$$

where β is the fraction of the counterions bound to the micelle, T the temperature, R the gas constant and X_{cmc} the mole-fraction of the surfactant in the liquid phase at the cmc, are summarized in Tables 2 and 4. It can be seen that ΔG_M° values are negative and large. It may be noted that the values are only semiquantitative as these are not exactly standard free energy changes. The ΔG_M° values reported in the literature diverge very much due to the use of different equations⁷ with and without β term. So it is plausible that in the present case, the apparently higher values of ΔG_M° is due to the inclusion of β in the equation and also may be due to the higher uncertainties in the β values.

Assuming that the aggregation number and the degree of ionization of the surfactant are temperature-independent, the standard enthalpy of micellization, ΔH_M° was calculated using phase separation model. The ΔH_M° value was calculated using the equation (similar to that of Clapeyron-Clausius equation), $\Delta H_M^\circ = [-RT^2 d/dT \ln X_{\text{cmc}}]$ and the data are included in Tables 2 and 4. Here it may be noted that the results are only semiquantitative. The ΔH_M° values of SDS and CPC are negative and become more negative with the increase in dielectric constant of the medium. The entropy

Table 5. Summary of effect of variation in concentration/dielectric constant and temperature of the medium on cmc of SDS (medium : acetonitrile-water system)

Mole fraction of acetonitrile, X	Dielec. const. of medium ϵ	cmc, 10^3 M		
		25°	30°	35°
0.000	78.54	8.2	8.1	8.0
0.103	78.10	8.1	7.9	7.7
0.322	76.08	7.8	7.7	7.5
0.508	65.67	7.0	6.8	6.7
0.716	60.79	6.6	6.4	6.2
0.918	53.23	6.4	6.3	6.1

Table 6. Summary of effect of variation in concentration/dielectric constant and temperature of the medium on cmc of CPC (medium : acetonitrile-water system)

Mole fraction of acetonitrile, X	Dielec. const. of medium ϵ	cmc, 10^4 M		
		25°	30°	35°
0.000	78.54	7.0	7.5	9
0.103	74.02	7.5	10	12
0.322	64.39	8.0	11	12.6
0.508	56.20	8.9	12	14
0.716	47.07	11	12	17
0.918	38.22	21	22	31

of micellization (ΔS_M^0) values are all small and negative and the values decrease with the increase in dielectric constant of the medium. Some earlier workers^{1,7} also reported such negative ΔS_M^0 . The small negative values of ΔS_M^0 and/or negative ΔH_M^0 indicate that micellization is not always entropy-controlled. The traditional view that the micellization is always entropy-controlled was challenged by Evans *et al.*¹⁶. We feel that the aggregation of surfactant is always accompanied by a decrease in translational and rotational freedom of surfactant monomer as they move from the bulk solvent into the confines of a small aggregate. Thus the entropic driving force must be negative and the driving force for micellization can be due to decrease in enthalpy. However, in the absence of any data (direct ΔH_M^0), it is not possible to arrive at any definite conclusion.

Although there is no phenomenological basis in thermodynamic functions, it has been observed that a linear relationship does exist between ΔH_M^0 and ΔS_M^0 . Occurrence of such linear relationships are referred to as compensation phenomena. The slope of such compensation lines has the dimension of temperature and the compensation temperature (T_c) for SDS and CPC are 4.3×10^{-3} , 3.8×10^{-3} K, respectively.

From the present investigation it can be inferred that cmc of SDS slightly decreases with the increase in amount of acetonitrile in acetonitrile-water mixed solvents as well as with the temperature, whereas in the case of CPC, cmc increases with the increase in concentration of acetonitrile in mixed solvent of acetonitrile-water as well as with temperature. The ΔG_M^0 , ΔH_M^0 and ΔS_M^0 are all negative. The small and negative values of ΔS_M^0 indicate that contrary to the general belief, micellization of SDS and CPC in mixed solvents of acetonitrile and water are enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled.

Experimental

Sodium dodecyl sulfate (Glaxo) and cetylpyridinium chloride (Sisco) were recrystallised from ethanol-water mixture and dried before use. Spectroscopic grade acetonitrile (Sisco) and double-distilled water were used to prepare different mole-fractions of acetonitrile in acetonitrile-water mixtures. The electrical conductivity measurement method was used to obtain cmc values. The specific conductivity was measured using a Systronic 304 conductivity bridge. Temperature of the solution was maintained constant ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) using a MLW U-10 thermostat. As the dielectric constants

of the mixed solvents are not readily available, they were calculated from the proportional contribution relation, $\epsilon = \sum x_i \epsilon_i$, where x_i and ϵ_i are the mole-fraction and dielectric constant of the *i*-th component, respectively. The cmc was determined from the plot of specific conductivity of the solutions vs surfactant concentrations.

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